

THE CHEMISTRY OF OLEO MARGOSA FROM *MELIA*
AZADIRACHTA OR NEEM OIL. PART I.
ISOLATION OF THE CONSTITUENTS
OF THE OIL.

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Six different substances have been separated from the oleo margosa or the neem oil. The main odoriferous constituent of the oil is a sulphur containing liquid of the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{30}O_3S$. A glucoside, which is the bitter principle of the oil, has been isolated. The latter appears to possess the formula $C_{28}H_{48}O_{10}$. Besides the oil consists of the glycerides of four acids, two of which (A and B) are saturated and the other two (C and D) are unsaturated. Of these the acid (A) (m.p. 67°) appears to be an isomer of tetradecoic acid, while the acid (B) (m.p. 55°), is most probably an isomer of palmitic acid. The unsaturated acid (C) belongs to oleic acid series and possesses the formula $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$. The fourth acid (D) belongs to the cyclic series of acid of the formula $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$.

Owing to the conflicting data about the neem oil and in view of its medicinal properties, it was thought necessary to put the oil as well as other portions of the tree to a closer examination.

Genuine samples of neem oil in quantity used in this investigation were procured from Birbhum, where the cultivators collect the seeds late in summer and then get them pressed for their own use as an insecticide and a fuel.

The physical data more or less agreed with those given by Chatterjee and Sen (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1920, **8**, 356). It contains a volatile odoriferous constituent together with a very bitter substance. These substances have now been isolated in fairly pure condition. Chatterjee (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1917-18, **5**, 656) attempted to free the oil of its odour by steam distillation and subsequently saponified it. The acid, isolated by him, must have contained the bitter principle. Chatterjee and Sen (*loc. cit.*) did not recognise that the bitter principle and the fatty acids in the oil might be independent of each other. Watson, Chatterji and Mukherji (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, **42**, 387T) attempted the separation of the different ingredients. But the method adopted by them did not appear to us to be very suitable.

The oil on keeping develops a rancid odour. It was, therefore, worked up very soon after receiving it from the source. It was first subjected to a process

of prolonged steam distillation until all volatile substances were removed. This distillate consisted of the odoriferous constituent of the oil mixed with a small quantity of a solid substance. This oil, however, on repeated distillation, was obtained as a colourless mobile liquid with a very penetrating and extremely unpleasant odour. This oil, designated as *Neemola*, contains sulphur. Analytical data and molecular weight suggest its molecular formula as $C_{15}H_{30}O_3S$. From about 30 lb. of crude neem oil only 15 g. of *Neemola* could be obtained. Further work on its constitution is now in progress.

The residue after steam distillation still possessed rather an unpleasant odour which was not quite as marked as that of the original oil. This oil was next extracted 5 to 6 times with water. The aqueous solution obtained from the residue of steam distillation was found to be extremely bitter, while the steam distillate, although possessed a highly obnoxious smell, did not taste bitter at all. The bitter principle was, therefore, present in the residual oil. On extracting it continuously with several litres of water, it was rendered far less bitter than the original oil. This aqueous solution yielded a mixture of a solid together with a little oil but the separation was not difficult. The bitter constituent of neem oil was thus obtained as a solid which has been called "*Margosin*". This was purified, analysed and found to be free from sulphur, thus differing from the observations of Sen and Banerji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 773). It analysed for a glucoside of the formula $C_{28}H_{48}O_{10}$. The degradation experiments with *Margosin* are now in progress.

The fatty oil remaining after the separation of *neemola* and *margosin* was saponified and from the potassium soap a mixture of four acids could be separated which appeared to be different from those of Roy and Dutt (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 333r) and Child and Ramanatham (*ibid.*, 1936, 55, 124r). One of these acids melted at 67° but was found to be different from stearic acid. From analysis and molecular weight, it appears to be an isomer of tetradecoic acid of the formula $C_{14}H_{28}O_2$ which we have called *Neem Acid "A"*. Together with this acid another solid acid was isolated which melts at a lower temperature, *viz.*, 55° , but appeared to be a higher homologue of acid "*A*". Its analysis and molecular weight suggested it to be an isomer of palmitic acid, $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$; this we have called *Neem Acid "B"*. Hilditch and Murti (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1939, 58, 310) also isolated some acids; their observations are similar to those of Roy and Dutt (*loc. cit.*). It appears to us that the earlier workers were misled by the physical properties of the acids because we do not find any analytical data regarding the acids from the papers of these authors.

After the separation of the two solid acids, the mother-liquor still contained some acidic substance, which solidified on cooling. The acid was, therefore, distilled under reduced pressure when it was obtained as a mixture of a solid and an oily substance which could be mechanically separated.

This oily mixture of acids was, therefore, esterified. The methyl ester was fractionated into two distinct portions. Both the esters are unsaturated and from them two acids could be regenerated. The lower boiling ester, $C_{16}H_{30}O_2$ (the ester of the neem acid C) absorbs bromine giving a dibromo derivative, which decomposes partially on distilling under reduced pressure. The free acid generated from the ester was isolated as a solid after distillation. It appears to possess the formula $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$ and thus belongs to the oleic acid series.

The higher boiling ester, $C_{19}H_{34}O_2$, give a dibromo derivative which also decomposes partially on distillation. From it, the acid $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$, isolated after hydrolysis, solidified partially at the ordinary temperature on standing for some time. This has been called Neem Acid "D", and apparently belongs to the cyclic series of acids perhaps similar to hydnocarpus or chaulmoogric acids. These acids are under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oil that was obtained from the market was filtered and the physical properties were determined. It was found to have $d_4^{22.9} = 0.9108$ and $n_D^{22.9}$, 1.46185. Its iodine value was found to be 69.56 and saponification value, 198.8.

Neemola (Odoriferous Constituent of Neem Oil).—Neem oil (220 g.) was subjected to steam distillation (sand-bath being replaced by a water-bath to prevent decomposition of the active principle). Some oily globules together with some solid particles distilled over with steam. After six litres of distillate were collected, no further oily globules came over with steam. The distillate from 1 kg. of oil was cooled in ice and saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted three times with ether. The ethereal extract, dried over magnesium sulphate, furnished after removal of solvent a pungent and nauseous smelling light yellow liquid. The oil was carefully and slowly distilled under reduced pressure from a glycerine-bath, the receiver being cooled in a freezing mixture. The first fraction collected at $150-60^\circ/110$ mm. was a light brown mobile liquid with the most acrid smell. On redistillation it had b.p. $156-58^\circ/118$ mm. [Found: C, 61.94; H, 9.81; S, 10.86; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 289.3. $C_{15}H_{30}O_2S$

requires C, 62.2; H, 10.3; S, 11.07 per cent. M.W., 290]. It is distinctly acidic being soluble in sodium carbonate solution from which it is reprecipitated on acidification. It immediately decolourises bromine but is not bitter in taste. It gives no ferric chloride reaction.

The second fraction, collected at $200-210^{\circ}/7$ mm., was a thick viscous mass and solidified on keeping. The solid crystallised from petroleum ether and proved identical with neem acid "B" (*vide supra*).

Margosin (the Bitter Principle of Neem Oil).—The solution left with oil after steam distillation, tasted very bitter. This was mixed with aqueous extract of the oil with water (5 times) and then examined for the bitter principle. But subsequently it was found better to extract the oil by a continuous process with hot water. The aqueous extract was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The oily brown residue, which was extremely bitter, was triturated with petroleum and then extracted with hot chloroform. The chloroform solution was then thoroughly washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%). It was then charcoaled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The chloroform was removed on the water-bath when a light yellow amorphous mass was obtained, which was further purified by washing with hydrochloric acid solution and then by precipitation from ether solution with petrol. The purified sample was obtained as a light yellow amorphous powder, m.p. $193-95^{\circ}$ (decomp). [Found: C, 62.01; H, 8.91; M.W. (ebullioscopic), 575. $C_{28}H_{48}O_{10}$ requires C, 61.76; H, 8.8 per cent. M.W., 544]. It is neutral in reaction and reduces Fehling's solution after hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid. It is probably a glucoside. We designate it as margosin. It shows no reaction with bromine in chloroform solution and does not give ferric chloride reaction.

Isolation of the Acids A, B, C and D from Neem Oil.—200 G. of the oil were hydrolysed on a gently boiling water-bath with 100 g. of potassium hydroxide in 450 g. of aqueous alcohol for 10 hours. The thick viscous material was cooled and was treated with water, when the potassium salts separated out as solid mass. These were collected, washed with cold water and subsequently acidified in aqueous suspension when a semi-solid mass of mixture of acids separated out. These were collected after cooling. On standing the precipitate became oily and the oily portion was freed at the pump as far as practicable. The solid residue was then triturated with petroleum ether, cooled at about 25° and then filtered. The filtrate on dilution with more petroleum and cooling to below 10° , gave some solid acids.

The crystalline solid acid mixture was triturated with just enough petroleum to give a thin paste, then cooled to about 25° and filtered by suction,

when the solid could be freed from most of the oily matter. But it was necessary to repeat the process several times before a complete separation could be effected. The solid residue was further purified by recrystallisation from petroleum when it had m.p. 67° . [Found : C, 74.21 ; H, 12.02 ; M.W. (ebullioscopic), 240 ; M.W. (by titration for a monobasic acid), 232.4. $C_{14}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 73.7 ; H, 12.2 per cent. M.W., 228].

The petroleum mother-liquor from the solid acid on cooling to 15° gave a second acid which melted at $50-53^{\circ}$. The filtration must be rapid otherwise the acid dissolves in the solvent with rise of temperature. This was purified by several crystallisations. Depending on dilution some times the solution was cooled to about $4-5^{\circ}$, before it crystallised. The purified acid "B" melts at 55° . [Found : C, 75.3 ; H, 12.2 ; M.W. (ebullioscopic), 260.2 ; M.W. (by titration, for a monobasic acid), 256.7. $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 75.0 ; H, 12.5 per cent. M.W., 256].

Separation of the Oil "X".—The oily product consisted of a mixture of two acids only. After removal of the solvent from the dried solution, the acid mixture (50 g.) was mixed with methyl alcohol (200 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (10 c.c., $d_{15} 1.84$) and esterified. The methyl alcoholic solution of the acids separated into two layers as soon as sulphuric acid was added. The mixture was heated on the steam-bath for about 7 hours when the layers practically disappeared. After removal of methanol and addition of water, the oily ester layer was purified in the usual way and distilled. The first fraction was collected at $205^{\circ}/14$ mm. and second at $215^{\circ}/14$ mm. After several redistillations the methyl ester of neem acid "C" had b.p. $177^{\circ}/3$ mm. [Found : C, 76.03 ; H, 11.7. M.W. (cryoscopic), 254. $C_{16}H_{30}O_2$ requires C, 75.6 ; H, 11.8 per cent. M.W., 253]. It had $d_4^{22.4}$, 0.84801 ; $n_D^{22.4}$, 1.443781, whence $[R_L]_D$ found : 78.28 (calc. 78.36). The ester absorbs bromine very rapidly. The bromo-ester, b.p. $230^{\circ}/4$ mm. (decomp.) gave low halogen values. (Found : Br, 31.4. $C_{16}H_{28}O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 38.4 per cent).

The neem acid "C", isolated by hydrolysis of the methyl ester, had b.p. $189-90^{\circ}/4$ mm. and m.p. $47-48^{\circ}$. [Found : C, 75.2, H, 11.57 ; $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$ requires C, 75.03 ; H, 11.66 per cent. Found : Ba, 22.13. $(C_{15}H_{27}O_2)_2Ba$ requires Ba, 22.3 per cent].

The second fraction (the methyl ester of neem acid D), on redistillation had b.p. $185^{\circ}/3$ mm. [Found : C, 77.5 ; H, 11.6. M.W. (cryoscopic), 302.9. $C_{19}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 77.6 ; H, 11.3 per cent. M.W., 294]. It had $d_4^{22.6}$, 0.86557 ; $n_D^{22.6}$, 1.44395, whence $[R_L]_D$ found : 89.57 (calc. 88.81). The ester rapidly absorbs one molecule of bromine and this bromo derivative also decomposes partially on distillation at $223^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : Br, 27.4. $C_{19}H_{32}O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 35.2 per cent).

The neem acid "D", isolated by hydrolysis, had b.p. 194-95°/4mm. and partially crystallised on standing, the crystals had m.p. 31-33°. [Found: C, 77.01; H, 11.7. $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 77.14; H, 11.43 per cent. Found: Ba, 19.3. $(C_{18}H_{31}O_2)_2$ Ba requires Ba, 19.7 per cent]. This acid also rapidly absorbs bromine at the ordinary temperature.

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